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MARKETING STRATEGIES AND MARKETING PERFORMANCE OF SEVEN-UP BOTTLING COMPANY, NIGERIA PLC.

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Abstract

The major objective of the study was to examine the effect marketing strategies on marketing performance of Seven-up Bottling Company, Nigeria Plc. The population of the study was 3500 and through the Taro Yamen's method of sample size determination, 359 respondents were selected. Findings from regression analysis in the study showed that product strategy was found to exert significant effect on customer patronage of Seven-up Bottling Company. This implies that changes in product strategy bring about positive and significant changes in customer patronage of Seven-up Bottling Company. Distribution strategy also exerts significant effect on sales volume of Seven-up Bottling Company as was found in the study. This equally shows that efficient distribution by Seven-up Bottling Company contributes to higher sales volume achieved by the company. Promotional strategy was found to exert significant and positive effect on market share of Seven-up Bottling Company. Lastly, it was found in the study that pricing strategy was found to be a positive and significant factor affecting profitability of Seven-up Bottling Company. This result implies that as Seven-up Bottling Company efficient pricing strategy, there profitability also increases. The researcher made the following recommendations amongst others; Seven-up Bottling Company, Nigeria Plc must first conduct proper marketing research to effectively understand the needs of their present and potential consumers. Such marketing research will go a long way in revealing the major needs of the consumers and thereby avail the company such opportunity of designing the right benefits for the customers. The use of arbitrary pricing strategy should be highly avoided. As products are manufactured for customers, the right price for each product offering should be adopted in order to ensure equity in pricing.

Keywords

Marketing Strategies,
Marketing Performance,
Customer Patronage, Efficient
Distribution

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INTRODUCTION

Marketing is the collection of human activities directed at satisfying needs and wants through a profitable exchange (Kotler, 2012). Strategy is borrowed from military literature, which refers to a plan of action (Anyanwu, 2012). However, marketing strategy is the broad principles and plan of action by which the business expects to achieve its marketing objectives in a targeted market (Kotler, 2012).

Business environment for manufacturing firms is very dynamic following the increased effects of globalization and development in information communication technology among other variables. In order for organization to align their operations to the dynamic operational environment, they have to constantly formulate and implement strategies (Johnson and Scholes, 2008). A strategy is an important component of organization planning towards the attainment of organizational objectives (Rajasekar, 2014). Strategy translates plans into actions and the intended results so as to deliver on organizational objectives. Successful strategy operationalization is whether actual operational results is at per with targeted results or superseded the outcome as set out in the strategic plan (Adeniji, 2013). Failure to achieve the set targets signifies weak strategy, which has been poorly operationalized. Well-implemented strategies promote overall organizational performance while poorly implemented strategies manifest themselves in poor performance results (Raduan, 2009). Strategic planning is an element of strategic management, it is the process and approach of specifying an organization's objectives, developing policies and plans to achieve and attain these objectives, by allocating resources so as to implement the policies and plans (David, 2005). Marketing performance is also an element of organizational performance; it is described as an organization's ability to acquire and utilize its scarce resources and valuables or expeditiously as possible in the pursuit of its marketing operational goals (Griffin, 2006). The essence of marketing strategies on marketing performance has been the focus of intensive research efforts in recent times. This is because business environment of manufacturing firms is changing rapidly and this change is characterized by such phenomena as the globalization, changing customer and investor demands, and ever-increasing product-market competition to compete successfully in this environment. Organizations continually need to improve their performance by reducing cost, innovating products and processes and improving quality, productivity and speed to market (Griffin, 2006). There is therefore the need for not just strategic management, but its implementation to achieve organizational, and specifically, marketing objective.

Strategic planning is an ongoing process that evaluates and controls the business and the industries in which the company is involved. It also assesses its competitors and set goals and strategies to meet all existing and potential competitors. It then reassess each strategy annually or quarterly, that is, regularly to determine how it has been implemented and whether it has succeeded or needs replacement by a new strategy to meet changed circumstances, new technology, new competitors, a new economic environment, new social, financial or political environment (Adeyeye, 2014). Marketing strategies help firms achieve a competitive and comparative advantage position and enhance its firm performance relative to their competitors, which are the main objectives, SMEs in particular, should strive to attain (Raduan, 2009).

Objectives of the Study

The major objective of the study was to examine the effect marketing strategies on marketing performance of Seven-up Bottling Company, Nigeria Plc. However, the specific objectives of the study were to:

- i. Ascertain the effect of product strategy on customer patronage of Seven-up Bottling Company;
- ii. Determine the effect of distribution strategy on sales volume of Seven-up Bottling Company;

- iii. Ascertain the effect of promotional strategy on market share of Seven-up Bottling Company;
- iv. Determine the effect of pricing strategy on profitability of Seven-up Bottling Company.

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were stated for the study.

- Ho₁:** Product strategy has no significant effect on customer patronage of Seven-up Bottling Company.
- Ho₂:** Distribution strategy has no significant effect on the sales volume of 7'Up Bottling Company.
- Ho₃:** Promotional strategy has no significant effect on the market share of 7'Up Bottling Company.
- Ho₄:** Pricing strategy has no significant effect on profitability of Seven-up Bottling Company.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Framework

Marketing Strategy

Marketing strategy is deciding in advance what to do, how to do it and who is to do it. Thus, marketing strategies bridges the gap between where we are, and where we want to be. Thus, marketing strategies makes it possible for things to occur which would not otherwise happen. Marketing strategies is however not a magic work that direct activities in a definite order, variation may occur despite the plans but without planning all event are left to chance. Marketing strategy can also be defined as the process of coping with business uncertainty by formulating future marketing course of action to achieve specific marketing results.

Dimensions of Marketing Strategies

A. Product Strategy

[Kotler and Armstrong \(2006\)](#) define a product as anything that can be offered to a market for attention, acquisition, use, or consumption that might satisfy a want or need. They further define a consumer product as the product bought by the final consumer for personal consumption. Consumers buy products frequently, with careful planning, and by comparing brands based on price, quality and style. [Borden, \(1984\)](#) sees a product as about quality, design, features, brand name and sizes. [Mohammad et al, \(2012\)](#) also say that product is the physical appearance of the product, packaging, and labeling Information, which can also influence whether consumers notice a product in-store, examine it, and purchase it. Past researchers have clearly suggested that product influences have a significant impact on business performance ([Kazem and Heijden, 2006](#); [Kemppainen, Vepsäläinen, and Tinnilä, 2008](#); [Ogunmokun and Esther, 2004](#); [Owomoyela et al, 2013](#)),

B. Pricing Strategy

[Kotler \(2007\)](#) defines price as a cost of producing, delivering and promoting the product charged by the organization. [Zeithaml \(2008\)](#) is of the view that monetary cost is one of the factors that influence consumer's perception of a product's value. Price can be

stated as the actual or rated value of a valuable product that is up for exchange; some define it as amount of money paid for product (Kotler *et al.*, 2005). In the studies of Colpan (2016); Doole *et al.*, (2006) and Owomoyela *et al.*, (2013) they establish significant relationship between price and business performance. The price you set for your product or service plays a large role in its marketability. Pricing for products or services that are more commonly available in the market is more elastic, meaning that unit sales will go up or down more responsively in response to price changes (Jones, 2017).

C. Promotion Strategy

Zeithaml *et al.* (2005) describe promotion as part of specific effort to encourage customers to tell others about their services. According to Duncan (2005), promotion is the key to the market exchange process that communicates with present and potential stakeholders, and the general public. Every firm or store must cast itself into the role of communicator and promoter. Hakansson (2015) also reports that promotion appears as an issue of how to create an optimal mix of marketing communication tools in order to get a product's message and brand from the producer to the consumer. Borden, (2004) defines promotion as sales promotion, advertising, personal selling, public relations and direct marketing. Kotler, (2007) discovers that Promotions have become a critical factor in the product marketing mix, which consists of the specific blend of advertising, personal selling, sales promotion, public relations and direct marketing tools that the company uses to pursue its advertising and marketing objective. Previous researches (Amine and Cavusgil, 2011; Francis and Collins-Dodd, 2014) have established significant relationship between promotion and business performance.

D. Place (Distribution) Strategy

Jones, (2017) defined place as any way that the customer can obtain a product or receive a service. Bowersox and Closs (2016) give distribution as another name for place. According to them, it is the third element of the marketing mix, and it encompasses all decisions and tools, which relate to making products and services available to customers. Kotler and Armstrong (2006), also define place or distribution as a set of interdependent organizations involved in the process of making a product available for use or consumption by consumers. Place strategy calls for effective distribution of products among the marketing channels such as the wholesalers or retailers (Berman, 2016). Owomoyela *et al.*, (2013); Amine and Cavusgil, {2011}; and McNaughton, (2002) agree that place has significant effect on business performance.

Marketing Performance

The concept of marketing performance is designated to evaluate the performance of an enterprise in relation to other firms in a given market or industry (Best, 2014). The term is complex and relative because it is based on the firm whether in manufacturing or service and at the time on the type of industry in which the firm operates (Robert and Harry, 2014). In any enterprise, competitive strategies are directed to achieve competitive advantage (Porter, 1980; 1985; 2000; 2012). However, the effective achievement of competitive advantage can only be worthwhile if there is effective achievement of stable marketing performance by the enterprise (Best, 2014).

Therefore, there is the need to direct all the marketing, business and competitive strategies to achieve sustainable marketing performance and competitive advantage (Shepered *et al.*, 2010). The enterprise as a result, ensures the smooth, systemic and

systematic implementation of plans, policies and programmes, which are much needed for the control of business and marketing activities so as to maximize efficiency and profitability. This will help the enterprise to measure the performance of the enterprise against its competition (Porter, 2012).

There are some indicators of marketing efficiency that can help to measure the marketing performance of small and medium scale enterprise. These are customer satisfaction, customer patronage, customer loyalty, sales volume, market share, profitability and at times competitive advantage (Best, 2014; Robert and Gathinji, 2014; Abiodun and Harry, 2014). These indicators are discussed herein.

Customer Patronage

This refers to the purchases of the product of the enterprise; that is the quantity of what the customers buy from the enterprise output (Tresh, 2011). It is the patronage of the customers that constitute company sales in a target market (Shepherd et al., 2010). With emphasis on customer value, the enterprise will increase the rate of adoption, frequency of purchases and customer loyalty in an industry (market) over the long run (Talaja and Ercegovia, 2013).

Sales Volume

Sales volume is the quantity of sales made by an enterprise over a specific time period. This comes from customer patronage; and can be quantified into monetary terms like naira, dollar or in other units like cartons, cans, crates, liters etc. (Best, 2014). Sales volume is the multiplication of the unit sales to the prices of the goods sold (Robert and Gathinji, 2014).

Some enterprises design some strategies to achieve immediate sales. This they easily do through some aggressive selling strategies, which are (easily) adopted to track unprecedented marketing opportunities to achieve return on investment (ROI) at the expense of long-term market share and sustainable profitability. This has affected the long-run growth and survival of these firms (Shepherd, 2011; Best, 2014).

Market Share

Market Share represents the percentage of the market a particular enterprise has captured in relation to the total market for a particular product (goods or service). It is also the number of customers which the enterprise can control (service) given the total demand in the market or the industry for the product (Tresh, 2011). This can be computed by taking the sales of the enterprise over the period and divide it by the total sales of the industry (market).

Market share is a function of approximation and relative industry definition (Tresh, 2014; Shepherd et al., 2014). It is through market share that we can determine the degree of competition existing in an industry. Thus, an industry in which no firm has large market share is typically more competitive than one in which one firm or a few have a large market share. In addition, one of the ways to access the competitiveness in an industry, especially the ones occupied by large firms is the "Concentration Ratio" (Shepherd et al., 2014).

However, another dimension for determining market share is through the market position of the firms participating in the industry; where have market leaders, market challengers, market followers and market nichers (Best, 2014). By this analysis, market leaders occupy about 40% (0.4) of the market share; market challengers occupy like 30%

(0.3%) while the market followers occupy 20% (0.2). Lastly, 10% (0.1) of the remaining market share is occupied by market nichers in the given industry.

The enterprise device some competitive strategies (both offensive and defensive ones) to either achieve or maintain or even increase its market share in the industry in which it operates (These offensive and defensive competitive strategies, even the co-operative ones have been discussed under market focus and strategic alliance strategies in this work.

Profitability

Profit is the difference between the income (revenue) and expenditure (cost or expenses) of an enterprise in the course of its businesses, exchange and transaction over a period of time (Robert, 2015). Profitability on its own is the percentage difference between absolute profit figures recorded at different periods. These differences are usually expressed in percentage to determine variations: whether profit is increasing, constant or decreasing, thereby showing the rate of these variations (Tresh, 2011).

Profitability, and not just the absolute profit, is the concern of an enterprise management, because it is one of and not the parameters to measure market performance. This is because it (profitability) is not the major index of the marketing performance, effectiveness and efficiency; as other indicators like customer satisfaction, patronage, sales volume market share, cost advantage, etc. can have a long-term overlapping effect on the performance of modern enterprises. This position has led to some contemporary firms to sacrifice some percentage profit to gain and sustain competitive advantage at the long-run using market share increase. These firms are called "Profit-Sacrificers", (Tresh, 2011).

There is no doubt that traditional firms seem particularly interested in profit, but present day firms are interested in sales maximization (Tresh, 2011). Maximizing sales requires reducing the price of the output of the enterprise, so as to sell larger volumes with the consideration of the cost of the business of the enterprise. This position captures the notion of Simon (2006) in Tresh (2011) that firms, despite the size are Profit Sacrificers in a bid to gain long-term performance; hence, maximizing sales sacrifices some profit (Tresh, 2011).

Theoretical Framework

Resource Based View Theory

The RBV school of thought explains the role played by resources owned and possessed by an organization in differentiating it from other organizations in the industry (Baumol, Litan & Schramm, 2009). These resources take different forms including total assets expressed in monetary terms, experience of key human resources and the overall personnel adequacy. Other measures include networks among other variables (Bhide, 2000). According to Spanos and Lioukas (2001), the RBV can be used to explain the differences in competitive positions enjoyed by different organizations in a given industry. Through the resources owned and utilized in the production process, organizations are able to outperform their competitors and emerge winners (Rumelt, 1984 and Barney, 1986).

The RBV is founded on the premise that organizations compete based based on their resources and capabilities (Peteraf and Bergen, 2003). Most RBV researchers (Bhide, 2000; Peteraf and Barney, 2003; and Foss and Knudsen, 2003) the resources affect an organizations ability to execute its game plan strategies which in turn affects organizational

performance. This theory is relevant for this study because it explains the role played by internal resources controlled by an organization in the level of performance recorded.

Empirical Evidence

Several studies have been conducted on marketing strategies and marketing performance for instance, [Njagi and Kombo \(2014\)](#) established that strategy implementation affected the level of performance reported by commercial banks in Kenya. The strategies defined the direction that the banks adopted in gaining competitive advantage and differentiating their financial service offerings from other commercial banks in Kenya. The results indicated that commercial banks in Kenya employed different strategy implementation programs on different strategies with the aim of leveraging their operational efficiency for better return on equity and assets. The banks controlled different resources that they combined in different proportions to achieve competitiveness in the industry. In order to be more competitive and responsive to customer needs, the study recommended continuous improvement on information communication and technology in their operations for operational efficiency.

[Rajasekar \(2014\)](#) examined how different factors affect among electricity distribution companies in the Sultanate of Oman by addressing the role played by organizational communications in strategy implementation. Among key factors in strategy implementation included types of leadership, structure of the leadership positions and internal control mechanisms. In a highly competitive current environment, organizations need to adopt various strategies including human resource management and internal competencies.

[Mbaka and Mugambi \(2014\)](#) conducted a study on strategy implementation in the Water Sector in Kenya through descriptive design. The study studied various secondary data reports on how various water projects were implemented. The findings show that strategy implementation in the water sector was affected to a large extent by the level of management support, inadequacy of resources and technical expertise among staff. The findings further indicated that strategy implementation was affected by the type of management leadership and the communication effectiveness.

[Ndegwah \(2014\)](#) studied strategy implementation in learning institutions by focusing on public Secondary Schools in Nyeri County, Kenya. The study collected primary data using a semi-structured questionnaire to collect data. The explanatory variables of the study included: Managerial skills, Resources allocation, Rewards & Incentives and Institutional policies. The targeted respondents included institutions' Principals who were free to delegate to their Deputies in the 2 Sub-counties: Mukurweini and 34 in Othaya. The findings show that: Resources allocation Managerial skills, Institutional policies, and Rewards/Incentives greatly affected marketing strategy implementation. Proper management of these factors had a great influence on marketing strategy implementation among secondary schools in the study area.

METHODOLOGY

In this research, the researcher adopted the descriptive research design. The population of the study was 528 staff of Seven-up Bottling Company, Aba, Abia State. The sample size for the study was determined through Taro Yamane's sample size determination formula. Using this formula, a sample size of 227 was obtained and used in the study. Convenience sampling which is a non-probability sampling method was employed in the study because it offered the researcher the opportunity to select and interview those who

were willing to provide the relevant information needed for the study. The researcher approached these respondents in their enterprises where copies of the questionnaire were administered to them and retrieved after completion. Based on a total sample size of 227, copies of the questionnaire were administered. All data obtained from the respondents were analysed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. All analyses were done according to the stated objectives of the study. Simple linear regression was further used to test the hypotheses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The analysis of data followed the stated objectives of the study and is as follows:

Effect of Product Strategy on Customer Patronage of Seven-Up Bottling Company

Table 1: Simple regression analysis showing the effect of product strategy on customer patronage of Seven-up Bottling Company

Model	B	Std. Error	t-value
(Constant)	5.606	0.527	10.639
Product Strategy	0.322	0.117	2.752**
R	0.678		
R ²	0.552		
F-ratio	26.688		
N	220		

Source: Survey Data, 2024

*Note: ** = Significant at 5% level*

In simple regression Table 1 above, product strategy was found to exert significant effect on customer patronage of Seven-up Bottling Company. The coefficient of determination r^2 was 0.552 showing that changes in product strategy can bring about 55% of the variation observed in customer patronage of Seven-up Bottling Company. Similarly, the r-value of 0.678 signifies a positive and direct relationship between product strategy and customer patronage of Seven-up Bottling Company. The f-calculated value was 26.688 and significant at the 5% level indicating that the model correctly fits. The estimated regression equation shows that customer patronage of Seven-up Bottling Company is a linear function of product strategy.

Effect of Distribution Strategy on Sales Volume of Seven-Up Bottling Company

Table 2: Simple regression analysis showing the effect of distribution strategy on sales volume of Seven-up Bottling Company

Model	B	Std. Error	t-value
Constant)	4.451	0.285	15.626
Distribution Strategy	0.596	0.201	2.956**
R	0.568		
R ²	0.462		
F-ratio	24.470		
N	220		

Source: Survey Data, 2024

*Note: ** = Significant at 5% level*

In simple regression Table 2, distribution strategy was found to exert significant effect on sales volume of Seven-up Bottling Company. The f-calculated value was 24.470 and significant at the 5% level indicating that the model correctly fits. The estimated regression equation shows that sales volume of Seven-up Bottling Company is a linear

function of distribution strategy. The coefficient of determination r^2 was 0.462 indicating that changes in distribution strategy can bring about 46% of the variation observed in sales volume of Seven-up Bottling Company. This further conforms to *a priori* expectation and shows that sales volume of Seven-up Bottling Company is bound to increase with effective distribution strategy. This assertion is at the 95% confidence level.

Effect of Promotional Strategy on Market Share of Seven-Up Bottling Company

Table 3: Simple regression analysis showing the effect of promotional strategy on market share of Seven-up Bottling Company

Model	B	Std. Error	t-value
(Constant)	4.412	0.222	19.840
Promotional Strategy	0.698	0.221	3.158**
R	0.873		
R ²	0.761		
F-ratio	27.911		
N	220		

Source: Survey Data, 2024

*Note: ** = Significant at 5% level*

Simple regression Table 3 above shows that promotional strategy exerts significant and positive effect on market share of Seven-up Bottling Company. The f-calculated value was 27.911 and significant at the 5% level indicating that the model correctly fits. The estimated regression equation shows that market share of Seven-up Bottling Company is a linear function of promotional strategy. The coefficient of determination r^2 was 0.761 indicating that changes in promotional strategy can bring about 76% of the variation observed in market share of Seven-up Bottling Company. This further indicates that the higher the use of promotional strategy by seven-up Bottling Company, the higher their market share. This further conforms to *a priori* expectation and shows that Seven-up Bottling Company will experience increase in market share with an increase and proper use of promotional strategy. This assertion is at the 95% confidence level.

Effect of Pricing Strategy on Profitability of Seven-Up Bottling Company

Table 4: Simple regression analysis showing the effect of pricing strategy on profitability of Seven-up Bottling Company

Model	B	Std. error	t-value
(Constant)	4.479	0.293	15.312
Pricing Strategy	0.054	0.011	4.909***
R	0.798		
R-square	0.741		
F-ratio	21.623		
N	220		

Source: Survey Data, 2024

*Note: *** = Significant at 1% level*

From the simple regression Table 4, pricing strategy was found to be a positive and significant factor affecting profitability of Seven-up Bottling Company. Pricing strategy was statistically significant at the 1% probability level and positively affects profitability of Seven-up Bottling Company. This result implies that as Seven-up Bottling Company efficient pricing strategy, their profitability also increases. The F-calculated value in the simple regression above was 21.623 and significant at the 1% probability level indicating that the model

specification was correct. The r^2 was 0.741 showing that 74% of the variations in profitability of Seven-up Bottling Company are explained by pricing strategy.

Discussion of Results

The study investigated the perceived influence of marketing strategies on performance of Seven-up Bottling Company, Aba in Abia State. In the light of regression outcomes, the current research has pointed out that there is a positive significant association with (99%) confidence interval between marketing strategies and marketing performance. The findings of the study that marketing strategies have a significant impact on marketing performance of Seven-up Bottling Company, Aba in Abia State. This suggests that the adoption and implementation of marketing strategies have a substantial impact on marketing performance of Seven-up Bottling Company, Aba in Abia State. The findings align with the assertions made by [Gbolagade, Adesola, and Oyewale \(2013\)](#), who posited that the marketing strategy of a product exerts a substantial impact on the performance of a business. The present findings provide support for the previous research conducted by [Mustapha \(2013\)](#), who similarly argued that the product encompasses its tangible attributes such as its physical look, packaging, and labeling information. The study reveals a strong correlation between marketing strategies and the marketing performance of Seven-up Bottling Company, Aba in Abia State, which aligns with the findings of [Wawira \(2016\)](#). Wawira's analysis of the marketing mix demonstrated that factors such as quality assurance, brand popularity, product diversification, packaging, and production volume significantly impacted market share.

CONCLUSION

The study has sought out to reveal how different marketing strategies can improve the marketing performance of Seven-up Bottling Company, Nigeria Plc. The aspects of marketing strategies considered were pricing strategies, promotion strategies, distribution strategies, and product strategies. As Seven-up Bottling Company, Nigeria Plc. strives to make profitable returns through the satisfaction of their various customer needs; the above marketing strategies have to be properly integrated to achieve such objective. Various products can be priced attractively to attract customers who will be satisfied by the value offered by such services. Similarly, the right promotional strategies that will include the design of persuasive messages and the selection of the right media will enhance the ability of Seven-up Bottling Company, Nigeria Plc. to effectively reach their target audience.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Following the findings of this study, the researcher has made the following recommendations:

- i. Seven-up Bottling Company, Nigeria Plc. must first conduct proper marketing research to effectively understand the needs of their present and potential consumers. Such marketing research will go a long way in revealing the major needs of the consumers and thereby avail the company such opportunity of designing the right benefits for the customers.
- ii. The use of arbitrary pricing strategy should be highly avoided. As products are manufactured for customers, the right price for each product offering should be adopted in order to ensure equity in pricing.
- iii. The interest of Seven-up Bottling Company, Nigeria Plc. when advertising should be to choose the medium/media that has/have a wider coverage and reachability considering

the huge financial outlay involved in advertising. Such skillful and careful selection can help the company save more from the use of unproductive media.

- iv. Customer service staff should be properly trained in the areas of complaints handling and problem solving. This will help in reducing the amount of time spent in handling customers' complaints and further reduce long queues observed at many customer service centers.

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